

Pilgrimage sites associated with the Noyon Khutagt Danzanravjaa

also known as “Energy Center”, “Khamarin Khiid”

By Saskia AbrahmsKavunenko, The University of Copenhagen

Entry tags: Religious Group, Buddhist Traditions, Religious Place, Open-Air Sanctuary, Monastery, Sacred Territory, Sacred Land, Sacred mountain

The sites associated with the lifetime of the Noyon Khutagt Danzanravjaa (1803-1857), the fifth reincarnation in the Noyon Khutagt lineage, in the Dornogovi aimag (province) form an important pilgrimage route in Mongolia. Danzanravjaa was born in the Gobi desert to a poor family during the Qing Empire. He is renowned for being an egalitarian lama (Buddhist religious specialist), a healer, and an influential playwright. The Energy Centre, which is one of the key sites on the pilgrimage is where he is believed to have left his healing energy for those who needed to benefit from its restorative properties following his death. Many of the other sites are associated with Danzanravjaa's life. One spot on the pilgrimage marks the site of Mongolia's first theatre which was destroyed during the socialist purges of the 1930s. His play *The Life Story of the Moon Cuckoo* (Saran Khökhöo Namtar) is one of Mongolia's most famous plays. Another site is a collection of crumbling meditation caves used by Danzanravjaa and his students, which include a rebirthing cave, an old cherry tree which has miraculously survived in the desert (donated to Danzanravjaa by a Japanese student), and a healing rock. Most of the artefacts associated with Danzanravjaa's lifetime managed to survive the socialist purges of the 1930s. When his temple Khamarin Khiid became under threat, the curator of the temple, Lama Tuduv, hid crates of artefacts in the Gobi Desert. Two months later soldiers arrived and ransacked the temple, destroying the temple and killing many of the resident lamas. During the purges of the late 1930s around 36,000 people, half of whom were Buddhist lamas, were killed. Lama Tuduv survived and taught the whereabouts of the hidden artefacts to his grandson. In 1991 his grandson Altangerel dug up the crates and most of the artefacts are now housed in the Danzanravjaa museum in Sainshand. Important parts of the pilgrimage now include: Tontoon oboo, the Energy Centre, the 108 meditation caves, the Ikh Tenger (great sky) Bell, the old site of the theatre, the newly built Khamarin Khiid temple complex, Bayanzurkh mountain, and the Danzanravjaa Museum at Sainshand.

Date Range: 2015 CE - 2015 CE

Region: Dornogovi province Mongolia

Region tags: Asia, Mongolia

Dornogovi province Mongolia near the Sainshand soum center

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Kollmar-Paulenz, Karénina. 2017. 'Energy for Tourists and for Pilgrims: Khamaryn Khiid and the Shambhala Energy Centre in Mongolia', *Asiatische Studien - Études Asiatiques*, 71 (4): 1293-1322.
- Source 2: Abrahms-Kavunenko, Saskia. 2021. 'Regeneration and the Age of Decline: Purification and Rebirth in Mongolian Buddhist Economies.' In *Monks, Money, and Morality* (eds.) Christoph Brumann, Saskia Abrahms-Kavunenko and Beata Świtek. New York: Bloomsbury Publishing: 179-194.
- Source 3: Kohn, Michael. 2006. *Lama of the Gobi: The Life and Times of Danzan Rabjaa Mongolia's Greatest Mystical Poet*. Ulaanbaatar: Maitri Books.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.iias.asia/sites/default/files/2020-11/IIAS_NL40_19.pdf
- Source 1 URL: <https://treasuryoflives.org/bo/biographies/view/Danzanravjaa/13588>

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

- I don't know

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Elevation

Type of elevation

- Mountain
- Gorge

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

- Yes

Type of feature

- Other [specify]: The pilgrimage sites have many human made structures: these include stupas, placards, meditation caves, statues and temples.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

- No

Notes: However in the nearby township of Sainshand is the Danzanravjaa museum (Mong. Данзанравжаагийн музей) which contains statues, personal items, ritual items and writings from Danzanravjaa.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The settlement of Sainshand (which is a soum centre) is located around 40 kilometres northwest of the key pilgrimage sites. There are also a number of ger camps (tourist accommodations made up of nomadic felt dwellings) nearby to accommodate pilgrims.

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: Most pilgrims travel to the pilgrimage site on the sleeper train from Ulaanbaatar train station. Upon arrival at Sainshand station taxi drivers wait for pilgrims and take them to the various pilgrimage sites. There is also a bus available from Sainshand and many people drive to the pilgrimage sites.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: Taxis with guides accommodate people travelling from the nearest urban center (Sainshand) to the pilgrimage sites.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: The pilgrimage sites contain many varied structures built for different purposes. These include sacred rock cairns (ovoo), Buddhist temples, meditation caves, stūpas, a bell, plaques, and statues.

↳ A single structure

– No

Notes: The pilgrimage sites contain many varied structures built for different purposes

↳ One single feature

– Mound

Notes: Mounds in the form of rock cairns are present at the pilgrimage sites.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: There are a number of sites associated with the life of Danzanravjaa and these are integrated into a pilgrimage route. These include: the Tontoon ovoos or Mööm ovoos which contains two stupas or ovoos (which in this case are breast like structures which people circumambulate), The Energy Centre (which contains many stupas), the temples with the Khamariin Khid (Хамарын хийд) complex, a bell, a commemorative plaque to mark the first theatre of Mongolia, and structures/statues/ovoos associated with the Bayanzurkh Uul (mountain).

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: Most of the structures (which are not naturally occurring features of the countryside) were constructed in the postsocialist period. Except for the 108 meditation caves, many of which have crumbled into the Gobi desert.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: There are a variety of features, both human constructed and naturally occurring on the pilgrimage. One of the most revered of these is the red sand within the Energy Center where Danzanravjaa is said to have left his energy.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The pilgrimage area is considered by many of the pilgrims to be sacred.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Healing

Notes: Most pilgrims visit the sites associated with the Noyon Khutagt Danzanravjaa for their restorative properties. It is common for students to visit the pilgrimage sites before their exams to improve their grades, for help with their own or a family member's illness (some people will ring a family member or friend from the Energy Center so that they can gain the benefits of the pilgrimage), and for help with other mundane needs. Some will go to the pilgrimage sites for

spiritual purification, whilst others visit for tourist purposes. It is generally believed that undertaking a pilgrimage to these sites will assist in refreshing one's vital energies (or khiimori, windhorse).

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– I don't know

Notes: At the time I visited in 2015 there was at least one temple in the Khamarin Khiid temple complex that was under construction.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

Notes: It is likely that the site was used in the pre-Buddhist period for rituals and for trade. Most Buddhist temples were built on ritually/strategically important sites.

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: The temples at Khamarin Khiid were destroyed during the 1930s socialist purges. When it was clear that the temple was going to be destroyed and ransacked the temple's curator, Lama Tuduv, packed the temple's artifacts into crates and hid them in the Gobi desert. Two months after Lama Tuduv hid the crates soldiers arrived at the temple and destroyed it and the remaining contents, killing many of the resident lamas. In the socialist purges of the 1930s over 36,000 people were murdered in Mongolia. Around half of this figure were lamas. During the socialist period, which ended with the Mongolian Democratic Revolution of 1989-1990, Lama Tuduv taught his grandson, Altangerel, the whereabouts of the hidden crates. In 1991, a few months after Lama Tuduv's death, Altangerel dug up the crates and the contents are housed in the Danzanravjaa Museum in Sainshand. The structures at Khamariin Khiid, the mountain of Bayanzurkh, the Tontoon Ovoo and the Energy Center were all built in the postsocialist period.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

Notes: However, the Energy Center is where Danzanravjaa is said to have left his energy for those in need of its curative properties.

Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: However, the sites may be used for carrying out shamanic ceremonies wherein the shaman channels their ancestors.

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– I don't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– I don't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– I don't know

Notes: It is likely that funding sources for the building of the stupas at the Energy Center and the temples at Khamarin Khiid were funded by external sources. This may have been funding from wealthy urban Mongolians or foreign donors, for a discussion of transnational funding networks see Abrahms-Kavunenکو, Saskia. 2019. Enlightenment and the Gasping City: Mongolian Buddhism at a Time of Environmental Disarray. Ithaca: Cornell University Press.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The construction of the temples was partially motivated by the increase in enthusiasm

for Buddhist religious practice and exemplars from the presocialist period that followed the end of the socialist period (see Humphrey, Caroline. 1997. 'Exemplars and Rules: Aspects of the Discourse of Moralities in Mongolia.' In *Ethnography of Moralities*, edited by Signe Howell, 25–48. London: Routledge).

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: However, the Danzanravjaa Museum at Sainshand was created with this purpose.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The Energy Centre is a patch of red earth where the sand is a unique dark red colour (a notable shift from the surrounding hues of the Gobi desert which are dull browns and greys). The red sand is semi-enclosed by a set of small white stūpas which form a porous mandala. Tontoon ovoo, to the north of the Energy Centre, is built on a natural rise in the landscape. From this point one can view the rising sun. The important structures, the ovoo (sacred rock cairn) and the statues on Bayanzurkh are built at key points on the mountain which itself is sacred. The (now mostly crumbled) meditation caves are built in a valley.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– No

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Notes: Whilst there is no strict hierarchy as such points on the pilgrimage are more important to visit than others. The Energy Centre is undoubtedly the most important part of the pilgrimage.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– I don't know

Notes: A small fraction of the area as the area itself is expansive.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Notes: The stūpa within the Khamariin Khiid temple complex was the largest single structure (that wasn't a temple) of the many structures built at the pilgrimage site.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: The stūpas are likely made from concrete or bricks.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Many of the structures are decorated on the outside. The stūpas at the Energy

Centres tend to be relatively unadorned and painted white. One of the structures at the Energy Centre is painted red emblazoned with the eyes of the Buddha. Ovoos (sacred rock cairns) are often covered in polyester prayer scarves (khadags) and prayer scarves.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: There are decorative elements within the temples at the temple complex of Khamarin Khiid. These include statues, paintings and ritual offerings.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Buddhist deities are depicted within the temples at the Khamarin Khiid complex

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The eyes of the Buddha are present at the Energy Centre

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The eyes of the Buddha are present at the Energy Centre. For some pilgrims the Buddha was a historical figure and philosopher for others he was (also or exclusively) a deity/supernatural being.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There are many representations of the windhorse (khiimori) at the pilgrimage sites

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Notes: Some decorative elements within the temple complex are non-figural such as the wheel of dharma and the eight auspicious symbols.

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: Geometric shapes do form part of the exterior of the temples in the Manchu style.

↳ Floral motifs

– I don't know

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– I don't know

Notes: Mongol bichig (traditional Mongolian script) and Tibetan are likely present as decorative features within the temple complex.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Decorative elements such as the eight auspicious symbols are also found on prayer scarves which adorn the sacred rock cairns (ovoo).

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– I don't know

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– No

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: There is a prominent statue of a Buddha at Bayanzurkh mountain and there are statues of Buddhist deities within the temple complex at Khamarin Khiid.

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: There is a statue of the Buddha at Bayanzurkh mountain and a statue of Danzanravjaa next to the Danzanravjaa museum in Sainshand

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: There is a statue instantiating the vital energy of the windhorse (khiimori) at Bayanzurkh mountain.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– I don't know

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– I don't know

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– I don't know

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: The Buddhist temples at Khamarin Khiid contain thangkas (Buddhist paintings in the Vajrayana style) depicting Buddhist deities.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– I don't know

Notes: Its probable that various Buddhist myths and hagiographies are represented within the temples at Khamariin Khiid.

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: There is at least one painting depicting Danzanravjaa within the Danzanravjaa museum

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: There are painted decorative elements at the Khamarin Khiid temple complex

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– I don't know

↳ Other type of decoration:

– I don't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Notes: The Energy Centre contains a depiction of the eyes of the Buddha.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: There are paintings of Buddhist deities in the temples at Khamarin Khiid

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– I don't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– I don't know

Notes: Buddhist doctrinal elements, such as the wheel of dharma, are likely present within the temples at Khamarin Khiid

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: There are depictions of the Buddha who can be perceived as being either human or supernatural. There is also a statue of Danzanravjaa next to the Danzanravjaa museum.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– I don't know

↳ Human narratives

– I don't know

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: There is a bell called the Ikh Tenger bell which we were told if we rang three times would dispell fears and fulfil wishes.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: The pilgrimage sites are not for worshipping the dead as such. Rather they are for connecting to Danzanravjaa's energy. This energy is believed to have apotropaic and healing qualities.

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– I don't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Notes: Though it is possible that shamans channel their ancestral spirits here

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Notes: The presence of local spirits and of Buddhist deities at these sites is likely

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:

– No

Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: In a sense. The energy of Danzanravjaa is said to be felt. People described being

energised or refreshed after visiting the pilgrimage sites.

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Danzanravjaa is thought by many people to be a semi-divine historical figure. For some he was an instantiation of the Buddhist teachings, for others a playwright, for others a powerful healer, for others a controversial egalitarian historical figure. He is thought to have left his healing powers at the Energy Centre.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: The energy of Danzanravjaa is felt by people. This could be conceived of as a form of communication with a human-divine being.

↳ In dreams:

– I don't know

↳ In trance possession:

– I don't know

Notes: It is possible that other forms of activities by Buddhist or non-Buddhist religious specialists occur at these pilgrimage sites.

↳ Through divination practices:

– I don't know

Notes: It is probable that some forms of divination (at least in the form of astrological readings) occur within the Khamarin Khiid temple complex.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: It is said that his restorative energy is accessible to all. There does not need to be a religious specialist present. Indeed, laypeople may act as conduits and pass the healing powers of the Energy Centre to family members or friends through the use of mobile phones.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The form of communication that is experienced here is generally felt through an enlivening of vital energies.

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– I don't know

Notes: Not specifically unique to the pilgrimage sites as far as I am aware. However as Mongolia is thought to be inhabited by spirits of various kinds and this is considered to be a powerful site, it is probable that there is some supernatural monitoring present.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Do visitors communicate with gods:

– I don't know

Notes: It is possible that some people feel connections to spirits or Buddhist deities whilst visiting the pilgrimage sites.

Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Notes: It is possible that some pilgrims feel connections to supernatural beings when they visit these pilgrimage sites.

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

Notes: Many people make offerings of milk, vodka and other items at different points in the pilgrimage but these are not mandatory.

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

Notes: It is not common to offer expensive items as far as I am aware. However people might make generous donations to temples and give valuable food offerings to temples and statues.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Oblations of milk are offered to Tontoon ovoos by women as they circumambulate the ovoos. People (both men and women) offer milk to the rising sun. Offerings of vodka are made in one of the meditation caves near Khamarin Khiid.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– I don't know

Notes: It is likely that some (or all) of the Buddhist stūpas contain offerings that are not visible.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: There are offerings of enclosed sacred vases within some of the meditation caves. These vases which contain unknown materials are often offered to people's homeland (nutag) and are bought at religious goods stores.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Notes: It seems likely that someone or a group are looking after the pilgrimage sites.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (rare)

Notes: Attendance is completely optional

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– Yes

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

↳ Birth

– No

↳ Transition to adulthood

– No

↳ Death

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Many students come to the pilgrimage sites before their exams.

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

Notes: There are many sites that most people visit in a particular way when they arrive (those there is no set route as such). Many people will follow the advice of family members, trusted friends or guides when they visit the pilgrimage. We were advised to first visit the Tontoon owoo where the women in our group circled the ovoos three times offering oblations of milk and saying the mantra "om maritze man sohar." Then we greeted the rising sun with our palms facing towards the sun and everyone in our group made oblations of milk. Then we went to the Energy Centre (which is characterised by stūpas in a porous mandala) and we encircled it clockwise inwardly doing activities in many of the locations. Our guide then took us to the 108 meditation caves (including the womb cave and the healing rock), to the Ikh Tenger bell (which we rang), to the old site of the theatre, to the newly rebuilt Khamarin Khiid complex. Afterwards we travelled to Bayanzurkh mountain. In the afternoon we travelled to Sainshand and visited the museum.

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– I don't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– I don't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Notes: As is typical of temples in Mongolia it is probable that the temples carry out soothsaying activities.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Danzanravjaa was considered to be a powerful healer in his lifetime. The Energy Centre is the site where he is believed to have left his healing energy for those who needed to benefit from its restorative properties (following his death). There are also places where one can purify their bad deeds (Bayanzurkh mountain) and be rebirthed (the womb cave in the meditation cave complex).

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– No

↳ Cleansing

– Yes

Notes: Many people come to the pilgrimage sites as a form of purification. Some of the sites are specifically associated with purification such as the womb cave (which is part of the 108 meditation caves, through which one crawls and is reborn (thereby cleansing you of previously accrued bad karma). At Bayanzurkh mountain there is a spot where people burn bits of paper with their bad deeds written upon them. Offering milk oblations is also seen in Mongolia as a form of purification.

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: People come to refresh their vital energies (khiimori) and to cleanse their bad karma and/or any inadvertent spiritual contamination.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– I don't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: There are many small rituals that take place at this site. Offering oblations of milk, circling important buildings, crawling through the womb cave, burning one's previous bad actions, rubbing oneself against a rock for its healing powers, lying or sitting on the red sands of the Energy Centre, and singing a song in reverence of Danzanravjaa are just some of the many activities.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: I don't know as I was not present at a large-scale ritual

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: I am not aware of large scale rituals. It is common for Buddhist temples to carry out morning sūtra readings (khurals)

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

Notes: However, it is common for people to follow advice from guides, trusted friends, family members, and other pilgrims.

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: As the sun rise people make oblations of milk together and raise their palms to face the rising sun.

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Notes: Being intoxicated or imbibing alcohol is not associated with this pilgrimage.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Religious specialists are present in the form of the lamas and the nuns that are associated with the Khamarin Khiid temple complex. However, they are not responsible for the activities carried out on the pilgrimages. Nor do they generally act as guides for pilgrims.

↳ Present full time

– I don't know

Notes: It is likely that some portion of the Buddhist religious specialists are present throughout the year

↳ Present part time

– I don't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Notes: Within Vajrayāna Buddhism there are hierarchies that the lamas and nuns fall within. As far as I know it is not specific to the pilgrimage sites as such but is part of a more general context.

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– I don't know

Notes: Not in the specific place as far as I know, though access to the top of the Bayanzurkh mountain is restricted to males

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– I don't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– I don't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– I don't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– I don't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Manuscripts and writings from Danzanravjaa's lifetime are preserved in the Danzanravjaa museum in Sainshand

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– I don't know

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Saskia Abrahms-Kavunenko. *Enlightenment and the Gasping City*. Cornell University Press. isbn: 9781501737664.

Reference: Christoph Brumann, Saskia Abrahms-Kavunenko, Beata Switek. *Monks, Money, and Morality*. Bloomsbury Publishing. isbn: 9781350213760.

Reference: Isabelle Charleux. *Nomads on Pilgrimage*. BRILL. isbn: 9789004297784.